

Efficacy of Smoking on Circulatory and Respiratory Indices of Smokers and Non-Smokers Sportsman

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to assess the effect of smoking on circulatory and respiratory indices of sportsman. A group of 40 University boys aged 21–24 years, who participated in All India Inter university level in the sports of Badminton, Basketball and football, volunteered to participate in this study. As per the requirement of the study the players were divided into two groups. i.e., smokers and non smokers. Each group comprised of 20 subjects. A smokers was a subjects who smoked more than ten cigarettes per day, and a non smokers was a subjects who had been not smoking at all. The circulatory indices was measured by using Stop watch, Stethoscope and Sphygmomanometer and respiratory indices was measured by Stop watch, Wet spirometer and Peak Flow Meter.

Results showed that there was a significant difference on that resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) between Smokers and non Smokers sportsman. Pulse pressure has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers, since the computed value of t for all the dimensions were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05 (19)} = 2.02$ except pulse pressure ($t=0.85$). The Results also indicate that resting respiratory rate, peak flow rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) has been found significant difference between Smokers and non Smokers sportsman. Vital capacity has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers, since the computed value of t for all the indices were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05 (19)} = 2.02$ except vital capacity ($t=0.01$). Finding showed non smokers sportsmen were better than smokers sportsmen on circulatory and respiratory indices.

Keywords: Smoking, Circulatory Indices, Respiratory Indices

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INTRODUCTION

Smoker says it is pleasant to smell and relaxes the mood and develops confidence towards life. A non-smoker says smoking is used as a custom, loathsome to the eyes, hateful to nose, harmful to brain and dangerous to lungs. So many scientific facts and evidences have been put forward to explain that smoking is harmful to health. Many smokers in spite of knowing this keep on smoking. Doctors who know all about it are found to be chain smokers. This shows that there exists some sort of psychological factor which plays the role when a person starts smoking and later on it develops physiological dependence due to which he is not able to leave the habit. Smoking in teenagers and adolescents indicates the psychology of this particular age group who want to break away from the bonds of adult authority as a reaction and experience the freedom by doing as they like. The glamor and to be

foremost among fashionable also facilitates this habit among the affluents.

The effect of smoking evidently does not depend upon the number of cigarette smoked as much as it depends upon the amount of smoke inhaled. Moreover, man's physical performance has a range of fluctuation which may mask the exact effect of tobacco among the moderate smokers.

Nicotine which is one of the important constituent of tobacco has a transient stimulatory effect on the nervous system followed by depression. Nicotine causes release of epinephrine from the adrenal glands which in turn stimulates the nervous system and other endocrine glands and causes the release of glycogen from the liver. The result is the feeling of stimulation or "kick" and relief from fatigue. This is however transient and is followed by further fatigue and depression. This explains the physiological dependence and why person likes to smoke again.

Acute inhalation of cigarette smoke may increase airways resistance and elevate blood carboxyhemoglobin because of the high concentration of carbon-monoxide in cigarette smoke. After having considered it may be said that smoking would have some definite effects on sports achievement of the higher level sportsmen.

Present study was planned to assess the effect of smoking on circulatory and respiratory indices of sportsman. The result would help to identify among smokers and nonsmokers, which group gives better result in circulatory and respiratory indices of sportsman.

METHODS

A group of forty (N = 40) male All India Inter university level in the sports of Badminton, Basketball and football players were in this study. The subjects were divided into two groups. i.e., smokers and non smokers. Each group comprised of 20 subjects. The average age of the students ranged from 21 to 24 years. A smoker was a subjects who smoked more than ten cigarettes per day, and a non smoker was a subjects who had been not smoking at all.

For measuring the breath holding time, resting respiratory rate and pulse rate, the stop watches were used. The suppliers, Krishna Watch Company, Mumbai, assured the accurate calibration of there watches. Blood pressure of the subjects was measured using Stethoscope and Sphygmomanometer. The Wet-Spiro meter used to measure Vital Capacity The peak Flow Meter was utilizes to measure Peak Flow Rate. The equipments were manufactured by a competent form, Biological concern, Kalkota. Thus the instrument reliability was assumed.

The subjects were clearly informed and well acquainted with the requirement of the study and the testing procedure. The testing on variables of resting pulse rate and resting respiratory rate was conducted in the morning in the respective rooms of the subjects, the tests on the rest of the variables was conducted at the human performance Laboratory of Lovely Professional University, Phagwara. The entire testing procedure took about 4 days.

The collected data were statistically analyzed using Medcalc software. Student's t-test was used to assess the between group differences. The level of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

The mean value of circulatory indices of smoker and non-smoker sportsmen is presented in Table-1.

It is seen from the Table 1 that the mean values of resting pulse rate and pulse pressure were lower for smokers and higher in non smokers. Blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) is lower for Smokers and higher in non Smokers. So it is understood that the resting pulse rate and pulse pressure is better in non Smokers than Smokers and blood pressure (Systolic) and blood pressure (Diastolic) is better in Smokers than non Smokers.

It is clear from the table value that resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) has been significant difference between Smokers and non Smokers. Pulse pressure has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers, since the computed value of t for all the dimensions were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05}$ (19) =2.02 except pulse pressure ($t=0.85$). Thus it may be concluded that the all the circulatory indices except pulse pressure among Smokers and non Smokers sportsmen found to be statistically significant.

It is seen from the table 2 that the mean values of resting respiratory rate were higher for smokers than the non smokers. Peak flow rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) is lower for Smokers and higher in non Smokers. In case of vital capacity the mean is equal for smokers and non smokers. So it is understood that the resting respiratory rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) is better in non Smokers than Smokers and Peak flow rate found no difference in mean for Smokers than non Smokers.

It is clear from the table value that resting respiratory rate, peak flow rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) has been found significant difference between Smokers and non Smokers sportsman. Vital capacity has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers, since the computed value of t for all the dimensions were greater than the tabulated $t_{0.05}$ (19) =2.02 except vital capacity ($t=0.01$). Thus it may be concluded that the all the respiratory indices except vital capacity among Smokers and non Smokers sportsmen found to be statistically significant.

Table 1: The Significant of Mean Difference, Standard Error of the Mean and Test Statistic t of on Circulatory Variables of Smoker and Non-smoker Sportsmen

Group Variable	Mean		SD		SEM		t-value	p-value
	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers		
Resting Pulse Rate(RPR)	63.8	58	5.46	9.40	1.22	2.10	2.08*	0.05
Blood Pressure (Systolic)	115.1	118.7	8.49	4.68	1.89	1.04	2.44*	0.02
Blood Pressure (Diastolic)	72	76.25	8.03	6.52	1.79	1.45	2.92*	0.008
Pulse Pressure (PP)	43.2	41.95	6.22	5.08	1.39	1.13	0.85	0.40

Fig. 1: Indicate the Mean Values (\pm SD), Standard error of the Mean and Test Statistic t of Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure (Systolic), Blood Pressure (Diastolic) and Pulse Pressure of Smokers and Non Smokers (N = 20) Sportsman

Table 2: The Significant of Mean Difference, Standard Error of the Mean and test STATISTIC t on Respiratory Indices of Smokers and Non Smokers Sportsmen

Group Variable	Mean		SD		SEM		t-value	p-value
	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers	Smokers	Non-Smokers		
Resting Respiratory Rate(RPR)	18.50	16.60	4.04	2.68	0.90	0.60	3.06*	0.006
Vital Capacity (VC)	3.46	3.46	0.49	0.44	0.11	0.09	0.01	0.98
Peak Flow Rate(PFR)	566.5	590.0	56.5	60.7	12.6	13.5	2.22*	0.03
Breath Holding (Positive)	54.75	65.85	12.7	26.6	2.86	5.96	2.28*	0.03
Breath Holding(Negative)	24.90	34.55	6.90	12.9	1.54	2.89	2.84*	0.01

Fig. 2: Indicates the Mean Values (\pm SD), Standard Error of the Mean and Test Statistic t of Respiratory Rate, Vital Capacity, Peak Flow Rate Breath Holding (Positive) and Breath Holding (Negative) of Smokers and Non Smokers (N = 20) Sportsmen

DISCUSSION

The calculation of circulatory indices has shows that there was a significant difference on resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic) between Smokers and non Smokers. Pulse pressure has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers sportsman, since the computed value of t for all the indices were greater than the tabulated $t_{.05} (19) = 2.02$ except pulse pressure ($t=0.85$). Thus it may be concluded that all the circulatory indices except pulse pressure among Smokers and non Smokers sportsmen found to be statistically significant.

The calculation of respiratory indices that resting respiratory rate, peak flow rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) has been found significant difference between Smokers and non Smokers sportsman. Vital capacity has been found insignificant difference between Smokers and non Smokers, since the computed value of t for all the indices were greater than the tabulated $t_{.05} (19) = 2.02$ except vital capacity ($t=0.01$). Thus it may be concluded that all the respiratory indices except vital capacity among Smokers and non Smokers sportsmen found to be statistically significant.

As per the finding non smoker sportsmen were better than smoker sportsmen on resting pulse rate, blood pressure (Systolic), blood pressure (Diastolic), resting respiratory rate, peak flow rate, breath holding (positive) and breath holding (negative) the finding of this study is supported by the finding of Oring and Jamison.

The finding of Moutis are in disagreement with the Finding of this investigation that of having insignificant difference on pulse pressure and vital capacity. Moreover research scholar has an observation that the difference between the pulse pressure and vital capacity between the smoker and non-smoker groups has been larger although not statistically significant. Moreover the smokers were not heavy smokers, they were moderate smokers. These reasons could be attributed to not getting significant differences on the indices as mentioned above.

CONCLUSION

In the light of conclusion drawn and with in the limitations of the study, it can be revealed that our bodily system have been gifted by nature to accommodate themselves and change the functions accordingly within the physiological limits. Smoking effects respiratory function due to carbon monoxide (CO present in its constituents) in the blood and reducing it's oxygen (O₂) carrying capacity. So the lower vital capacity of the smokers was due to the lesser

concentration of oxygen in the blood. This has been responded by cardio-vascular system by increasing the pulse rate which increases the amount of blood flow through lungs. Minutes to compensate the deficient oxygenation of blood.

No significant changes were found in pulse pressure and vital capacity of the smokers and non smokers. Hence, it can be concluded that the physical activity may help the moderate smokers by involving the adaptation power of there cardio-vascular and respiratory system.

After giving a deep view of all the tables, it can be observed that there is not much of difference in the blood pressure, but pulse rate is higher for smokers, which indicates that due to the physical activity. The individuals maintain certain physical values to the optimum level. They also compensate certain changed values, which were the Results of harmful effects of smoking. It may be said that the individuals who are involved in physical activity may adopt and tolerate the harmful effects of smoking in better way.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors would like to thank sports director of sports director, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab for providing assistance in collecting the relevant information for undertaking quality research. I am also grateful to Mr. Satpal Yadav and Dr. Amar Kumar for all the suggestions offered an encouragement given to me. My thanks are due to all the students who acted as a subjects for the study. With there voluntary and wholehearted support could not have been completed.

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